

AN EFFECTIVE METHOD FOR MODELING THE TENSION FRACTURE OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: A modeling method that uses finite element analyses together with a progressive damage model was developed to predict the fracture strength of composite shells with cut-outs subjected to in-plane tensile loads. The use of a progressive damage model for composites involves degrading elastic stiffnesses when material failures are detected. This material degradation can cause severe non-convergence difficulties in the solution process of the finite element analyses. This problem can prematurely terminate the finite element analyses and prevent accurate fracture strength predictions, especially for larger panels. In the developed modeling method, artificial viscosity was added to an existing material damage model to overcome the convergence problems. Fracture strength predictions using this modeling method compared well with experimental data for both small and large notched panels. Furthermore, the developed method was able to overcome convergence problems using the quasi-static solution procedure. This characteristic makes the developed modeling method much more computationally effective than modeling methods that require dynamic solution procedures, which are often used to partially treat the non-convergence problems.

KEYWORDS: damage tolerance, composite progressive failure, finite element modeling, artificial viscosity.

INTRODUCTION

Predicting notch strengths of composite laminates with cut-outs is an important and difficult modeling problem that has been studied extensively. This type of modeling is required to study the damage tolerance of composite structures such as airplane fuselages and other composite pressure vessels. Numerous analytical techniques ranging from semi-empirical fracture models to comprehensive numerical methods have been proposed [1]. Most existing modeling methods work well for small coupons, but are not effective for larger panels [2]. Large panels here indicate panels that are wider than ten inches. Comprehensive numerical methods are required to study the damage tolerance of structures with multiple failure modes. For example, there are three failure modes in a damage tolerance study of an airplane fuselage: skin fracture, stiffener failures, and skin/stiffener joint failures.

In this study, a modeling method that uses finite element analyses together with a progressive failure model was developed to simulate failures of large composite panels with cut-outs. Figure 1 shows the type of geometry and loads to be studied using this modeling method. In

this paper, notch strength predictions for flat notched panels under uniaxial tension are presented. The materials under consideration here are continuous fiber reinforced composite systems such as graphite/epoxy.

Figure 1: Geometry and loads to be studied

Modeling failures in composites is difficult for at least two reasons. First, the failure mechanism is complex. It involves many failure modes including fiber breakage, matrix cracking, and shear failures. These different failure modes cause different types of material degradation. In addition, these failure modes interact. To accurately predict notch strengths, the material model must capture the relevant and important failure modes and the corresponding material degradations. Second, the finite element analyses must overcome numerical problems caused by the material degradations. This material nonlinearity in composites is severe because the fibers, the main load carrying constituent, fail in a brittle manner. The brittle fiber failure introduces a singularity in the constitutive relations. This singularity can cause serious convergence problems in the nonlinear solution process of the finite element analyses. Furthermore, brittle failure is a form of strain softening, which may cause the results to be mesh sensitive [3].

The first problem, the failure mechanism, has been extensively studied and many composite progressive failure models have been proposed. In this study, a composite failure model recently developed by Shahid and Chang [4] was adopted. The focus of this study was on the second problem, for which there is very little reported work. The goal was to overcome numerical problems caused by the brittle fiber failure, so that accurate notch strength predictions could be made.

Although not studied extensively, the non-convergence problem is important to the notch strength modeling problem, especially for large panels. In small coupons, accumulated damage including fiber failure is normally confined to a small area at the notch before final failure occurs. However, for large panels, experiments have shown that damage can accumulate to a substantially larger area before final failure occurs [5]. The extensive damage could significantly reduce material properties in this area which could potentially cause the convergence problems. In the small coupon analyses, even if numerical problems prematurely terminated analyses, notch strength predictions based on maximum analysis loads can often be made without great loss of accuracy. This practice will often underpredict notch strengths of larger panels. For larger panels, numerical problems due to brittle fiber failures must be overcome to obtain accurate notch strength predictions.

NUMERICAL PROBLEMS

The numerical problems that prematurely terminated the finite element analyses include the non-convergence problem in the Newton-Raphson nonlinear solution scheme in most cases and floating point problems in a few other cases. Floating point problems can be cured by simply degrading stiffnesses to small, but non-zero numbers. However, the non-convergence problem is not trivial. A non-convergence problem is the condition where the solver can not find an equilibrium solution after several Newton-Raphson iterations inside a load increment, even after the load increment had been cut back several times. Note that Arc-length methods are not solutions to these problems. All analyses in this study were displacement controlled, and the displacement boundary condition was defined a-priori to increase monotonically.

The brittle material degradation caused by fiber failures in composite is the main cause of the convergence problem. Figure 2 shows this troublesome characteristic in the on-axis stress and strain behavior of a unidirectional ply subjected to a uniaxial tension load. This abrupt and total stiffness degradation is a singularity in the constitutive relations. The brittle degradation often causes two conditions that can lead to the non-convergence problem: shocks in the displacement field, and an ill-conditioned consistent tangent stiffness.

Figure 2: Abrupt stiffness degradation caused by fiber failure

A displacement field shock is a large and sudden jump in the structure deformation. This occurs when the loaded composite laminate adjusts itself to the directional stiffness loss. This directional stiffness loss is unique to brittle failures in laminate composites. For a “strain driven” finite element analysis, large deformation moves the solution (equilibrium displacement field) far away from the current displacement field, making it difficult for the nonlinear solution scheme to converge.

The consistent tangent stiffness is the coefficient matrix in the linear matrix equation used to advance the solution in the nonlinear solution scheme [6]. When this matrix becomes ill-conditioned, the solution scheme has more difficulty converging.

In the developed modeling method, an existing composite progressive damage model was adopted to model the failure response of composite structures, and artificial viscosity was added to this damage model to overcome the convergence problem. The following sections describe the modeling method, a brief description of the composite failure model, and the artificial viscosity material model. Notch strength comparisons between experimental data and model predictions are presented, together with the effects of the artificial viscosity on fracture strength predictions.

MODELING METHOD

The commercial finite element code ABAQUS/Standard [7], together with a user defined material model was used to predict notch strengths of notched composite panels. ABAQUS reduced integration layered shell elements S4R and S8R were used. The loads were uniaxial tension and were perpendicular to the cut-outs (first problem in figure 1). The load was applied quasi-statically by fixing the panel's bottom side and prescribing a displacement boundary condition to the top side (displacement control analyses). The full Newton-Raphson method (not modified Newton) was used in the nonlinear solution process. Finite deformation theory was used since large deformations were anticipated at the notch.

The quasi-static solution procedure makes this modeling method very effective computationally compares to modeling methods that require dynamic solution procedures. Although, the notch strength problem is a static problem, dynamic solution procedures are often used because it can partially improve the convergence characteristic of the analyses.

The composite progressive failure model used in this study was based on a model recently developed by Shahid and Chang [4], which describes the failure criteria, and degradation rules. This material model is a nonlinear elastic model (elastic with damage). Four failure modes are considered: fiber breakage, fiber compression failure, matrix cracking and shear failure. Modified Hashin's failure criteria were used to predict the failure modes [8]. Failures and damages are tracked in each ply, and ply stiffnesses are reduced based on the cumulative damage state of the ply. The constitutive relations are as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{xx}(d) & Q_{xy}(d) & 0 \\ Q_{yx}(d) & Q_{yy}(d) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{ss}(d) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where d is the material damage state, and Q_{ij} are stiffnesses.

The important degradation characteristic is that stiffness degradations are gradual and small for matrix cracking and shear failure modes, and the degradation is abrupt and total for the fiber failure modes (see figure 2). The degradations due to matrix cracking and shear failures cause no convergence problem in the analyses. However, the brittle degradation due to fiber failure can cause severe convergence problem.

To overcome the convergence problem caused by the fiber failure mode, artificial viscosity was added to the material model. The added artificial viscosity acts as a shock absorber and damps out displacement jumps and discontinuities in the stress and strain fields. The viscosity term also adds viscous stiffness to the material, which helps to keep the consistent tangent matrix from becoming ill-conditioned. The added viscosity will also help to reduce the mesh sensitivity problem [3].

The constitutive relations of the progressive damage model with the added artificial viscosity is as follow:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{xx}(d) & Q_{xy}(d) & 0 \\ Q_{yx}(d) & Q_{yy}(d) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{ss}(d) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} b(d)E_{xx}\dot{\epsilon}_{xx} \\ b(d)E_{yy}\dot{\epsilon}_{yy} \\ b(d)G_{xy}\dot{\gamma}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 b(d) &= 0 & t_f > t > (t_f+t_0) \\
 b(d) &= b_0[1-\frac{(t-t_f)}{t_0}] & t_f < t < (t_f+t_0)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_j$ are the strain rates, b_0 is the artificial viscosity parameter, t_f is the fiber failure time, and t_0 is the viscosity ramp down period. b_0 and t_0 are parameters required for the viscous model. However, a constant t_0 was used in this study so that the viscous model is essentially a simple one parameter model. Since the artificial viscosity may add undesirable effects to the analysis result, this viscosity should be added only when it is needed. In the current model, the artificial viscosity is added after the fiber failure mode is detected. The viscosity is also removed slowly over a predetermined period after this fiber failure occurs.

For quasi-static analyses, time in the strain rate equation is directly related to the “load” progression in the analysis. For example, if the total displacement boundary condition is applied at time 1.0, then half of this displacement boundary condition is applied at time 0.5. Figure 3 shows the effect of the artificial viscosity to the material degradation of a unidirectional ply subjected to uniaxial load.

Figure 3: Effects of artificial viscosity on the fiber failure mode

The artificial viscosity can change the results of an analysis; too much viscosity will increase a structure’s stiffness, and erroneously increase the notch strength prediction. Thus, it is important to use enough viscosity to overcome convergence problem, but not too much. For this modeling method to work, the problem must have a “proper range” of artificial viscosity. When using an artificial value in the proper range, assuming it exists, the artificial viscosity will be enough to overcome convergence problems, and will not cause error to the strength prediction. Figure 4 shows the idea of the “proper viscosity range” in an ideal problem.

The proper range of artificial viscosity is problem dependent, since the susceptibility of an analysis to convergence problems and the notch strength prediction depends on the loading, the geometry, the material, the discretizations, and the solution path. This means there is no a priori knowledge of the proper amount of viscosity, and analysis iterations may be required to obtain a valid notch strength prediction. Limiting the viscous model to one parameter (b_0) will simplify any required parametric studies.

Figure 4: Proper range of artificial viscosity in an ideal problem

MODEL VERIFICATION

Finite element analyses were performed to validate the developed modeling method for 11 test cases where notch strength experimental data was available. These test cases included 7 small coupons and 4 large panels. The small coupon test data was obtained from Sandia National Laboratories [9]. The large panel test data was obtained from the Boeing Company [5]. The load in all test cases was uniaxial tension. Table 1 shows the geometry, material, and lay-up for the test cases.

Table 1. Geometry, material and lay-up of test cases.

Case	w (mm)	a (mm)	R (mm)	Material	Lay-up
70B	38.1	6.35	6.35	T800/3900-2	$[(45/90/-45/0)_2]_s$
54B	38.1	6.35	6.35	T800/3900-2	$[-45/0/45/90_2/-45/90_2/45/0]_s$
76B	38.1	6.35	6.35	T800/3900-2	$[45/90/-45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45/0/\pm 45]_s$
70C	38.1	6.35	1.59	T800/3900-2	$[(45/90/-45/0)_2]_s$
70E	25.4	9.5	1.59	T800/3900-2	$[(45/90/-45/0)_2]_s$
54E	25.4	9.5	1.59	T800/3900-2	$[-45/0/45/90_2/-45/90_2/45/0]_s$
76E	25.4	9.5	1.59	T800/3900-2	$[45/90/-45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45/0/\pm 45]_s$
P8	914.	102..	0.89	AS4/938	$[\pm 45/90/0/\pm 60/90]_s$
P9	914	114.	0.89	AS4/938	$[\pm 45/0/90/\pm 30/0]_s$
P12	1524.	152.	0.89	AS4/938	$[\pm 45/0/90/\pm 30/0]_s$
P12 B	1524.	152.	0.89	AS4/938	$[\pm 45/90/0/\pm 60/15/90/\pm 60/0/90/\pm 45]$

For comparison, the same analyses were performed using the progressive damage model without the added artificial viscosity. Material properties and parameters required for the composite progressive damage model can be found in reference 4.

Table 2 summarizes notch strength results. These results show that analyses with and without artificial viscosity predicted the notch strength of small coupons well. Analyses without the viscosity severely underpredicted the notch strength of the large panels. Notch strength prediction for large panels using analyses with the viscosity compared well with experimental data.

Table 2: Failure load comparison

Test	Experimental data (N)	Model with viscosity (N)	Model w/o viscosity (N)
70B	45,400	47,200	47,200
54B	31,200	45,000	45,000
76B	50,300	57,000	57,000
70C	44,100	47,200	46,700
70E	16,900	21,500	21,400
54E	13,800	16,500	15,600
76E	25,800	27,100	25,400
P8	347,000	356,000	191,000
P9	316,000	312,000	169,000
P12	601,000	650,000	312,000
P12B	668,000	601,000	245,000

Table 3 shows the effects of artificial viscosity on failure load predictions for seven of the cases shown above. These results show that a low level of viscosity was required to overcome the non-convergence problem, and that failure load predictions were not very sensitive to the viscosity level.

Table 3: Effects of artificial viscosity on failure load prediction

Case	analysis 1		analysis 2		analysis 3	
	b_0	Failure load (N)	b_0	Failure load (N)	b_0	Failure load (N)
70B	1.E-5	47,200	1.E-4	47,200	1.E-3	50,700
54B	1.E-6	45,000	1.E-5	45,000	1.E-4	45,000
70C	1.E-5	47,200	1.E-4	48,000	1.E-3	51,200
70E	1.E-6	21,500	1.E-5	21,500	1.E-4	21,500
76E	1.E-6	27,100	1.E-5	27,100	1.E-4	32,000
P8	1.E-4	356,000	1.E-3	356,000	3.E-3	401,000
P9	1.E-4	312,000	1.E-3	334,000	3.E-3	343,000

CONCLUSION

It has been demonstrated that artificial viscosity can be used to overcome non-convergence problems caused by brittle fiber failures when modeling composites. A simple artificial viscosity model along with a modeling method on using this viscous model to predict notch strengths of composites has been presented. Together with the progressive damage model developed by Shahid and Chang [4], the developed artificial viscosity modeling method was successfully used to predict the notch strength of both small and large composites panels subjected to uniaxial tension load. The artificial viscosity modeling method allowed accurate notch strength predictions for large panels, which could not be effectively done previously.

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